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$L = Q(\sqrt{3})$ MAYDON USTIDA IKKINCHI SKALYAR KO'PAYTMANING TA'RIFI VA XOSSALARI

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Annotatsiya: Maqolada L maydon ustida ikkinchi ushbu $\langle x, y \rangle_2 = x_1y_1 - 3x_2y_2$ shakldagi bichiziqli forma olinib, $\{L, \langle x, y \rangle_2\}$ bichiziqli metrik fazoning geometriyasi o'rganildi. Q ratsional sonlar maydoni ustida $a + b\sqrt{3}, a, b \in Q$ shakldagi sonlardan iborat bo'lgan $L = Q(\sqrt{3}) = \{a + b\sqrt{3}, a, b \in Q\}$ ikki o'lchovli maydon va $\langle x, y \rangle_2 = x_1y_1 - 3x_2y_2$ shakldagi bichiziqli forma ishlatildi.

Kalit so'zlar: maydon, skalyar ko'paytma, ratsional son, bichiziqli forma, kommutativ.

Аннотация: В L статье изучалась $\langle x, y \rangle_2 = x_1y_1 - 3x_2y_2$ геометрия $\{L, \langle x, y \rangle_2\}$ билинейного $a + b\sqrt{3}, a, b \in Q$ метрического пространства путем принятия второй билинейной формы на поле. На поле Q рациональных чисел $L = Q(\sqrt{3}) = \{a + b\sqrt{3}, a, b \in Q\}$ использовалось двумерное поле, состоящее $\langle x, y \rangle_2 = x_1y_1 - 3x_2y_2$ из чисел вида u и линейного вида v .

Ключевые слова: площадь, скалярное произведение, рациональное число, линейная форма, коммутативность.

Abstract: In the L article, the $\langle x, y \rangle_2 = x_1y_1 - 3x_2y_2$ geometry of the $\{L, \langle x, y \rangle_2\}$ bilinear metric space was studied by taking the second bilinear form on the field. A two-dimensional Q field consisting of numbers of $a + b\sqrt{3}, a, b \in Q$ the form $L = Q(\sqrt{3}) = \{a + b\sqrt{3}, a, b \in Q\}$ and a linear form of the $\langle x, y \rangle_2 = x_1y_1 - 3x_2y_2$ form were used on the field of rational numbers.

Key words: area, scalar product, rational number, linear form, commutative.

Q ratsional sonlar maydoni ustida $L = Q(\sqrt{3}) = \{a + b\sqrt{3}, a, b \in Q\}$ shakldagi ikki o'lchovli maydon berilgan bo'lsin. Bu maydon ustida ikkinchi skalyar ko'paytmani quyidagicha aniqlaymiz: $a = a_1 + a_2\sqrt{3}, b = b_1 + b_2\sqrt{3}$ elementlar uchun quyidagi $\langle a, b \rangle_2 = a_1b_1 - 3a_2b_2$ ko'rinishda bo'ladi. Bu ifodani skalyar ko'paytmaning shartlariga tekshiramiz:

1. $\forall a, b \in L$ elementlar uchun, quyidagi

$$\langle a, b \rangle_2 = \langle b, a \rangle_2 (*)$$

tenglik bajarilishini ko'rsatamiz: Tenglikning chap tomonidan quyidagi $\langle a, b \rangle_2 = a_1b_1 - 3a_2b_2$ tenglik kelib chiqadi. Tenglikning o'ng tomonidan quyidagi $\langle b, a \rangle_2 = b_1a_1 - 3b_2a_2$ tenglik kelib chiqadi. Q ratsional sonlar maydonining kommutativligidan (*) tenglik bajariladi.

$\forall a, b \in L \forall \lambda \in Q$ elementlar uchun, quyidagi

$$\lambda \langle a, b \rangle_2 = \langle \lambda a, b \rangle_2 (**)$$

tenglik bajarilishini ko'rsatamiz: Tenglikning chap tomonidan quyidagi $\lambda \langle a, b \rangle_2 = \lambda(a_1b_1 - 3a_2b_2) = \lambda a_1b_1 - 3\lambda a_2b_2$ tenglik kelib chiqadi. Tenglikning o'ng tomonidan quyidagi $\langle \lambda a, b \rangle_2 = \lambda a_1b_1 - 3\lambda a_2b_2$ tenglik kelib chiqadi. Yuqoridagi tengliklardan ko'rinadiki (**) tenglik bajariladi.

$\forall x, y, z \in L$ elementlar uchun, quyidagi

$$\langle x + y, z \rangle_2 = \langle x, z \rangle_2 + \langle y, z \rangle_2 (***)$$

tenglik bajarilishini ko'rsatamiz. Tenglikning chap tomonidan quyidagi $\langle x + y, z \rangle_2 = (x_1 + y_1)z_1 - 3z_2(x_2 + y_2)$

tenglik kelib chiqadi. Tenglikning o'ng tomonidan quyidagi

$$\langle x, z \rangle_2 + \langle y, z \rangle_2 = x_1z_1 - 3x_2z_2 + y_1z_1 - 3y_2z_2 = (x_1 + y_1)z_1 - 3z_2(x_2 + y_2)$$

tenglik kelib chiqadi. Bu tengliklardan (***) tenglikning bajarilishi kelib chiqadi.

Demak, $\langle a, b \rangle_2 = a_1b_1 - 3a_2b_2$ ikkinchi skalyar ko'paytmasi uchun skalyar ko'paytmaning barcha xossalari bajariladi.

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